

Do Autotelic Personality and Study Techniques Help Students' to be Intrinsically Motivated?

Md. Enamul Hasan¹, S.M. Khaled Hossain²

Abstract

The aim of this research is to explore the motivational factors behind university (Undergraduate level) students having autotelic personalities and the intrinsic motivational orientation which may help them to have a focused career and vision. The attributes, or meta-skills include [a] curiosity, [b] persistence, [c] personal attitude, [d] materials control and [e] intrinsic motivation. We implemented a questionnaire survey and collected data from 240 undergraduate-level students. Employing structural equation model (SEM) with SmartPLS, our findings exert that students having the higher level of autotelic personality, control over the academic materials, curiosity, persistence lead them to be intrinsically motivated, which in return may help them to succeed in their further career. The findings of this study may be of interest to the students who faces dilemma in their preference setting arena as well as to the institutions to help students to enhance their skills in this regard.

Keywords: Autotelic personality, intrinsic motivation, structural equation model, university students.

1.0 Introduction

Students' motivation is a crucial fact in tertiary level education, specifically owing to the significance of academic achievement in their

¹ Md. Enamul Hasan is a Lecturer at Army Institute of Business Administration Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. His contact address: enamul@aibasavar.edu.bd

² S. M. Khaled Hossain is an Assistant Professor at Army Institute of Business Administration Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. He is also a PhD Fellow at Dept. of AIS, Jagannath University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. His contact address: khaled@aibasavar.edu.bd

career life. This research aims to find the aspects that will assist educational theorists in understanding students' attitudes toward learning, as well as what helps and inhibits learning. This will aid the educational community in predicting student academic achievement and identifying students before their grades start to decline (Kamauru, 2000). Lumsden (1994) found that children's desire to learn diminishes as they get older. Learning can sometimes feel more like a burden than a pleasure. As a result, a huge proportion of students drop out before graduating. Because of students' negative attitudes about education, only a small percentage of students are mentally present in the classroom. In these circumstances, students' motivation level can play a significant role in engaging them with their studies. Students' motivation is the factor that determines how students feel about the learning process. A number of studies have been undertaken to investigate the influence of student motivation on academic achievement. Lumsden (1994), for example, looked into students' involvement in education and the sources of their motivation. Marshal (1987) viewed student motivation as a force that is beneficial for the learners. According to Ames (1990), learning motivation is based on a long-term, high-quality attachment to learning and a commitment to the learning experience.

Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are frequently used to categorize student motivation. When a learner is inspired from within, he or she is intrinsically motivated. Intrinsically motivated students are compelled to learn for a variety of reasons, including curiosity, pleasure, or enjoyment, as well as to fulfil their own intellectual and personal objectives. Students who are intrinsically motivated, according to Dev (1997), do not require any form of reward or incentive to initiate or complete a task. This type of learner is more determined to accomplish the assigned task and is drawn to activities that are difficult. According to Lepper (1988), intrinsic motivation is valued for the pleasure it brings or the sense of accomplishment it generates. Thus, students who are intrinsically motivated are more enthusiastic, self-driven, and enjoy their studies, whereas students who are extrinsically motivated try to drag

themselves through academic assignments, feel compelled to learn, and always put forth minimal effort in order to receive maximum praise. Students who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to use tactics that involve more effort and allow them to process the information more thoroughly. Another important fact that might influence the intrinsic motivation level of the students is their autotelic personality. Many of the previous studies depicted that there exists a positive connection between autotelic personality of the students and their intrinsic motivation level (Jeng and Teng, 2008; Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Ning and Downing, 2010). The current study aims to investigate the motivating factors that lead university students to develop an autotelic personality, as well as the intrinsic motivational orientation that may aid them in developing a focused career and vision. The findings of this study may be of interest to the students who face dilemmas in their preference setting arena as well as to the institutions to help students to enhance their skills in this regard. In section 2 the researchers have reviewed the related literature on the subject matter whereas in section 3 the methodological aspects of the study were described. In section 4 the researchers analysed data and interpret the results and finally, in section 5 the study concluded their remarks.

2.0 Review of Related Literatures

2.1 Autotelic Personality and Intrinsic Motivation

"The word 'autotelic' is made up of two Greek roots: auto (self) and telos (destination)". An autotelic activity is one that we engage in only for the purpose of experiencing it. When it comes to personality, autotelic refers to someone who "does things for their own sake, rather than for the sake of achieving some eventual external aim" (Csikszentmihalyi 1997). "The ability to manage a rewarding balance between the "play of challenge finding" and the "work of skill building" is the main characteristic of the autotelic personality" (Csikszentmihalyi et al. 1993). The concept of autotelic personality was first conceptualized by Csikszentmihalyi in

1997 as a revised version of flow theory. In the flow theory, Csikszentmihalyi (2000) defined flow as a condition of intrinsic motivation in which a person is fully engaged in what he or she is doing for the sake of the action itself. It is characterized by a fusion of action and awareness, a sense of control, strong concentration, loss of self-consciousness, and time transformation (Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Csikszentmihalyi and Larson, 2014; Csikszentmihalyi and LeFevre, 1989; Nakamura and Csikszentmihalyi, 2002). The individuals who belongs autotelic personality prefer to put themselves in situations that allow them to experience flow states frequently (Csikszentmihalyi et al. 1993; Nakamura and Csikszentmihalyi 2002). Flow occurs when an individual finds a balance between the challenge of an activity and his or her own skills, according to Csikszentmihalyi's original paradigm (Csikszentmihalyi 2000). Csikszentmihalyi and Csikszentmihalyi (1988b) proposed in their revised model that flow occurs when both difficulties and capabilities are strong. Many of the previous literature (Jeng and Teng, 2008; Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Ning and Downing, 2010) argued that the individuals who possess autotelic personalities are more intrinsically motivated and self-driven in their work than those who do not.

Integrating the flow and autotelic personality literature, we understand autotelic personality as a multifaceted construct with four attributes: (a) curiosity and interest in life (b) persistence, (c) personal attitude, (d) materials control. In designing the present study we consider four attributes of autotelic personality namely students' curiosity, persistence, personal attitude, and materials control as independent variables which may affect the intrinsic motivation level of students characterized as the dependent variable.

The first attribute of autotelic personality is curiosity and interest in life. Curiosity has been shown to have a favorable association with students' intrinsic motivation in prior studies (Litman, 2005; Shroff et al., 2008). Curiosity stimulates an internal urge or needs to study new knowledge

or obtain information that learners have overlooked. This aspect has a direct impact on both students' intrinsic motivation and academic achievement. In a study of 581 university students in Hong Kong, Ning and Downing (2010) discovered that the students' motivation is the strongest predictor of their academic performance, but there have been few attempts to investigate more specific factors such as curiosity and external regulation to see if they affect intrinsic motivation among Hong Kong university students. The study discovered a strong link between students' intrinsic motivation and their curiosity.

H₁= There is statistically significant relationship between curiosity and intrinsic motivation level of students.

The second attribute of an autotelic personality is persistence. Grantt (2008) conducted a study in which he argued that there is a significant positive association between students' persistency with their intrinsic motivation level. According to the researcher, the students who are intrinsically motivated are more persistent with their studies in comparison to those who are not. In addition, the students who are persistent in their personality are more curious to learn new insights and take on new challenges, and because of that reason, they belong to more intrinsic motivation level for their study than the others.

H₂= There is statistically significant relationship between persistence and intrinsic motivation level of students.

The third attribute of autotelic personality is personal attitudes. The multitude of ways in which an individual responds to and communicates with others is defined as personality (Robbins & Judge, 2011). Despite being regarded by many experts as one of the most important aspects of human behavior and motivation, the relationship between personality and motivation is still poorly understood. Contrary to belief, personality attributes can even be a source of motivation (Ariani, 2015), as motivation is a powerful force that drives people to take action. Personality, according to Jeng and Teng (2008), can be a critical aspect in a variety of

situations where an individual's personality might influence his or her performance. Personality has a role in a variety of situations, reinforcing the argument that it should be a source of motivation (Lumanisa, 2015). Intrinsically driven students, according to Kaufman et al. (2008), are outgoing, agreeable, attentive, and open to new experiences. (Komarraju et al., 2009) revealed a link between the Big Five personality traits and academic motivation, as well as establishing numerous important personality-motivation correlations.

H₃= There is statistically significant relationship between personal attitudes and intrinsic motivation level of students.

The fourth attribute of autotelic personality is attentional control or materials control. Many of the earlier researchers have found a positive connection between students' materials control and their intrinsic motivation level. Fadlelmula (2010) claimed that the students who are more organized in controlling the study materials are more concentrated with their study due to their intrinsic motivation level. Students with intrinsic motivation assimilated reading material more carefully obtained higher grades, and showed more persistence than students with extrinsic motivation, according to Vansteenkiste, Simons, Lens, Soenens, Matos, and Lacante (2004). On the other hand, Bye et al., (2007) showed that students who have no control over their study materials face a lot of problems during their exams and consequently they lose their motivation level to study.

H₄= There is statistically significant relationship between materials control and intrinsic motivation level of students.

3.0 Research Methodology

For the purpose of this study, data were collected from the students of Army Institute of Business Administration, Savar, using self-administered questionnaire. We collected responses from 150 students with the questionnaire consisting two sections, Section A (Demographic

information) and Section B (Autotelic personality and intrinsic motivation related questions). The items used in to measure the Autotelic personality and intrinsic motivation were adapted from Tse et al. (2020). Respondents were asked to indicate their agreement or disagreement with several statements on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree.

4.0 Findings and Analysis

4.1 Convergent Validity

The convergent validity of the measurement is usually ascertained by examining the loadings, average variance extracted (AVE) and also the composite reliability (CR) (Gholami et al., 2013; Rahman et al., 2015). The loadings are all higher than 0.708, the composite reliabilities were all higher than 0.7 and the AVE of all constructs were also higher than 0.5 as suggested in the literature (See Table1 and Figure 2).

Table 1: Convergent Validity

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Cronbach	rhoA	AVE	CR
Curiosity	CU_1	0.785	0.7	0.718	0.621	0.831
	CU_2	0.753				
	CU_4	0.825				
Intrinsic Motivation	IM_2	0.834	0.676	0.701	0.604	0.820
	IM_3	0.713				
	IM_4	0.779				
Materials Control	MC_3	0.72	0.685	0.696	0.614	0.826
	MC_4	0.81				
	MC_5	0.816				
Personal Attitudes	PAT-1	0.833	0.847	0.812	0.638	0.876

	PAT-2	0.875				
	PAT-3	0.836				
	PAT-5	0.767				
Persistence	PE_1	0.773	0.811	0.848	0.686	0.897
	PE_2	0.809				
	PE_3	0.813				
	PE_4	0.799				

Source: Authors' calculation

4.2 Discriminant Validity

We have tested the discriminant validity using the new suggested method and the results are shown Table 2. If the HTMT value is greater than HTMT_{0.85} value of 0.85 (Kline, 2015), or HTMT_{0.90} value of 0.90 (Gold et al., 2001) then there is a problem of discriminant validity. As all the

Figure 1: Measurement Model Results

values passed the HTMT_{0.90} (Gold et al., 2001) and HTMT_{0.85} (Kline, 2015), indicating that discriminant validity has been ascertained.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity (HTMT Ratio)

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Curiosity					
2. Intrinsic Motivation	0.566				
3. Materials control	0.445	0.463			
4. Persistence	0.623	0.535	0.482		
5. Personal Attitude	0.562	0.508	0.53	0.646	

Source: Authors' calculation

5.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, we developed and validated 22-item questionnaire as an alternative to measure the influence of individuals' autotelic personality and possibility of being intrinsically motivated. Our findings posit that students having such personality are more target oriented and intrinsically motivated, which may help them to be successful and more ethical employee to the organization or in their business activities. The findings of this study may be of interest to the students who faces dilemma in their preference setting arena as well as to the institutions to help students to enhance their skills in this regard.

References

- Ames, C. (1990). Motivation: What teachers need to know. *Teachers college record*, 91(3), 409-421.
- Ariani, D. W. (2013). Personality and learning motivation. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(10).
- Bye, D., Pushkar, D., & Conway, M. (2007). Motivation, interest, and positive affect in traditional and nontraditional undergraduate students. *Adult education quarterly*, 57(2), 141-158.

- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1988). The flow experience and its significance for human psychology. *Optimal experience: Psychological studies of flow in consciousness*, 2, 15-35.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1997). Flow and education. *NAMTA journal*, 22(2), 2-35.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (2000). *Beyond boredom and anxiety*. Jossey-Bass.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M., & Larson, R. (2014). Validity and reliability of the experience-sampling method. In *Flow and the foundations of positive psychology* (pp. 35-54). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M., & LeFevre, J. (1989). Optimal experience in work and leisure. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 56(5), 815.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M., & Rathunde, K. (1993). The measurement of flow in everyday life: toward a theory of emergent motivation.
- Dev, P. C. (1997). Intrinsic motivation and academic achievement: What do their relationship imply for the classroom teacher? *Remedial and special education*, 18(1), 12-19.
- Fadlelmula, F. K. (2010). Educational motivation and students' achievement goal orientations. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 859–863
- Grant, A. M. (2008). Does intrinsic motivation fuel the prosocial fire? Motivational synergy in predicting persistence, performance, and productivity. *Journal of applied psychology*, 93(1), 48.
- Gholami, R., Sulaiman, A. B., Ramayah, T., & Molla, A. (2013). Senior managers' perception on green information systems (IS) adoption and environmental performance: Results from a field survey. *Information & Management*, 50(7), 431–438.

- Gold, A. H., Malhotra, A., & Segars, A. H. (2001). Knowledge management: An organizational capabilities perspective. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 18(1), 185–214.
- Jeng, S. P., & Teng, C. I. (2008). Personality and motivations for playing online games. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 36(8), 1053-1060.
- Kamauru, R. J. (2000). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Predict Academic Performance of College Students. *Morehouse College*.
- Kline, R. B. (2015). Principles and practice of structural equation modeling. Guilford publications.
- Kaufman, J. C., Agars, M. D., & Lopez-Wagner, M. C. (2008). The role of personality and motivation in predicting early college academic success in non-traditional students at a Hispanic-serving institution. *Learning and individual differences*, 18(4), 492-496.
- Komarraju, M., Karau, S. J., & Schmeck, R. R. (2009). Role of the Big Five personality traits in predicting college students' academic motivation and achievement. *Learning and individual differences*, 19(1), 47-52.
- Lepper, M. R. (1988). Motivational considerations in the study of instruction. *Cognition and instruction*, 5(4), 289-309.
- Litman, J. (2005). Curiosity and the pleasures of learning: Wanting and liking new information. *Cognition & emotion*, 19(6), 793-814.
- Lumanisa, A. (2015). *The Influence of Personality Traits and Motivational Factors in Predicting Students Academic Achievement* (Doctoral dissertation, Dublin, National College of Ireland).
- Lumsden, L. S. (1994). Student Motivation. *Research Roundup*, 10(3), n3.